

**Geo-Politizing the Intermediate Spaces of the World-System:
Semi-Cores and Semi-Peripheries, Geostrategies of Subordination and Autonomy (Cases in Latin America and Southern Europe After the Cold War)¹**

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Abstract:

This paper aims to deepen on a key yet obscure and imprecise concept, used primarily in world-systems analysis: the semi-periphery, and how it can be useful to explain the position of some countries in several geopolitical regions of the world. After a brief evaluation of the concept's theoretical importance, it reviews various empirical efforts to discern between countries' circumstances by the horizontal tripartite division of the world-economy's areas. It then analyzes its evolution – especially in the most recent decades after the Cold War – and verifies how heterogeneous the semi-periphery is. It then proposes to divide the category by distinguishing semi-centers from semi-peripheries. For this, it is necessary to politicize and “geo-politicize” the concept – that is, to include structural political and geopolitical elements upon its definition and analysis, which until now has based itself fundamentally on the geoeconomic structure. Doing so will also allow us to distinguish between subordinate and autonomous semi-peripheries in relation to the hegemonic contender powers. Some cases of semi-peripheries and semi-centers in different geopolitical orders will be discussed, and we will try to discern the different roles these countries have had in the world system. This would allow us to understand their roll nowadays.

Key words:

World System, semi-core, semi-periphery, Latin America, Southern Europe

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Introduction: “semi-periphery”, an obscure but necessary concept

In the more traditional core-periphery theories, the concept of “semi-periphery” does not exist. It is quite specific to world-systems analysis, as Immanuel Wallerstein and other authors have understood it, ever since André Gunder-Frank showed in his dependency theory that, in the process of exploitation of the periphery by the core, or, if you like, in the process of production of underdevelopment, the intermediate instances play a fundamental role:

“A whole chain of constellations of metropolises and satellites relates all the parts of the total system from its core in Europe or the United States to the most distant points in the Latin American countries. When we examine the metropolis-satellite structure, we find that each one of the satellites, including today’s underdeveloped Spain and Portugal, serve as an instrument to extract capital or economic surpluses from their own satellites and direct part of these surpluses towards the foreign metropolis of which are all satellites” (Frank, 1967: 162).

To move beyond the obvious examples of Spain and Portugal, the more “developed” satellites, such as the São Paulo region in Brazil, had their own satellites, so that within the same state there were structural situations more like the core and others definitely from the periphery. Frank was pessimistic about the possibility that the “industrial development” of São Paulo, for example, would have a definitive character and succeed in removing “Brazil from the cycle of satellite development and underdevelopment that has characterized its other regions and its national history up to now within the capitalist system” (Frank, 1967: 164). This article will not enter this debate, although I think that the example of Brazil can easily be contrasted with that of the United States, and thus show that the industrial development of a region can lead to the development of the entire state, even at the cost of a bloody war. What is interesting about Gunder Frank’s conceptualization for the present work is the affirmation of the existence of intermediate instances between the core and the periphery.

Later, Wallerstein specifically introduces the category of “semi-periphery” to refer to this phenomenon in the modern world-system, defining it precisely as being

“based on the double antinomy of class (bourgeois-proletarian) and function in the division of labor (core-periphery). The core-periphery distinct [...] differentiates those zones in which are concentrated high-profit, high-technology, high-wage diversified production (the core countries) from those in which are concentrated low-profit, low- technology, low-wage, less diversified production (the peripheral countries). But there has always been a series of countries which fall in between in a very concrete way and play a different role. The productive activities of these semi-peripheral countries are more evenly divided. In part they act as a peripheral zone for core countries and in part they act as a core country for some peripheral areas” (Wallerstein, 1976: 462-463).

But it must be understood that, in the case of the semi-periphery, “there are no semi-peripheral processes; rather, the term [...] is applied directly to the zones, regions or states in which neither the processes of the core nor those of the periphery predominate. This means that the general social relations that take place

in these zones suppose the exploitation of peripheral zones, at the same time that the same semi-periphery suffers the exploitation of the core” (Taylor and Flint, 2002: 22). That is, they are intermediate spaces that also play an intermediary role, but of a different nature in each case. In Wallerstein’s (1976) original definition, they include

- countries from Latin America (Brazil, Mexico, Argentina, Venezuela, and possibly Chile and Cuba);
- from the European periphery (all of the south, Portugal, Spain, Italy and Greece; most of the east, the German Democratic Republic and, although he does not specify it, Poland, Czechoslovakia, and Hungary; and parts of the north, such as Norway and Finland);
- Israel and some Arab countries (Algeria, Egypt and Saudi Arabia);
- Nigeria and Zaire, in Africa;
- Turkey, Iran, India, Indonesia, China, Korea and Vietnam, in Asia;
- and finally, the white countries of the Commonwealth (Canada, Australia, South Africa and New Zealand).

Later, in an important work on the evolution of semi-peripheries in different world-systems throughout history, Chase-Dunn and Hall (2018: 37-38) identify several types throughout history that mix different roles and positions:

- one that mixes core and peripheral forms of organization,
- one that can be located spatially between the core and peripheral regions,
- one that can be located spatially between two or more core regions in competition,
- one that performs mediation activities between the core and peripheral areas, and
- one in which the institutional characteristics are intermediate between those found in the core and the periphery.

In view of this heterogeneity of roles, the authors are cautious about the precision of the concept: “Classifying these different types of semi-peripheries continues to be both an empirical and a theoretical problem. Until more detailed comparisons between different types of world-systems are completed, it would be premature to define the concept of a semi-periphery more precisely” (Chase-Dunn and Hall, 2018: 37-38).

Other authors also believe that this definition is insufficient when constructing this category, as shown in the heterogeneity of countries in the Wallerstein list. In this sense, Terlouw (1993) qualifies the concept as “imprecise” or “elusive”. Boaventura de Sousa Santos (1985) calls it “descriptive”, “vague” and “negative”. It would be descriptive “because it barely has theoretical content, [in the Wallersteinian version] it is little more than a construction by analogy” with the middle classes (1985: 870). These are countries that would cushion the contradictions between those in the core and those in the periphery, in a similar way to the middle classes which play an intermediary role between the bourgeoisie and the proletariat. The concept would

be vague because “the criteria to define a peripheral status are many and difficult to quantify” (Santos, 1985: 870). And it would be negative because semi-peripheral states “lack materiality in themselves and do not have a particular evolutionary logic, and are a mixture of characteristics attributed to central or peripheral states and societies” (ibid.).

All these statements suggest that conceptualizing the semi-periphery is complex and problematic. In fact, I share with Domingues the idea that “it raises the most subtle theoretical and practical problems of our days” (2012a: 13). But we can base our analysis on the definition of Santos (1985), which emphasizes that the concept is associated with an intermediate situation and a certain capacity for intermediation. As an historical example, he gives the case of Portugal as an intermediary between the core sphere and the colonial sphere. But we cannot focus only on this specific situation because when it ended after April 25, 1974, the country could have stopped being “semi-peripheral” in its terms, but it did not. In other words, the semi-peripheries are changeable and in most cases ephemeral, but they have a fundamental role in modernity, which has become a global civilization but is heterogeneous (Domingues, 2012b).

It is necessary that semi-peripheries exist because they are key to balancing the world-system and reducing conflict. Like other triadic concepts —such as Lefebvre’s (1974) spatial “trialectics,” for example, in which spatial representations, spatial practices, and spaces of representation interact to produce space— the core–semi-periphery–periphery conceptualization is intended to provide stability to the system.

But it is important to understand that, at the same time, the movement of the system is also explained by this triadic character: in the case of Lefebvre, the “spaces of representation”, the third element of his trialectic, which refers to the thoughts and practices that in various ways contradict, or at least question, the dominant representations of space and the spatial practices that derive from them. “Spaces of representation” are fundamental to understanding change in space, because they allow resistance to those dominant practices and representations.

In the case of world-systems analysis, the semi-periphery plays a key role, because it allows us to understand the rise of regions and nations from the periphery to the core or the descent from the latter to the former. But this implies very different situations and processes, so the concept of “semi-periphery” to a certain extent becomes a “mixture”.

This article is fundamentally about theoretical reflection, and the case studies presented develop and support the theoretical constructions that I propose, although not necessarily prove them given their small number. In this sense, I adopt the comparative methodology, one of the most traditional in political science, since we do not carry out a single case study. Rather we examine a small selection of case studies in an already relatively small research universe, such as the set of units of the interstate system. In this way, although we cannot prove it, a relatively reduced set

of case studies will allow us to increase control over the hypothesis (Sartori and Morlino, 1999) about the necessary politicization of the concept of semi-periphery. In other words, comparative case studies, a type of case study that Lijphart (1971) proposed many years ago, will allow advancement in controlling the validity of the theory presented (Sartori, 1991).

It is not a question of exhaustively studying Latin America and Southern Europe, but of selecting cases in both regions that support the hypotheses about the semi-peripheries. In what follows, first I will review the forms that have been used to empirically differentiate the core, the semi-periphery and the periphery in the analysis of world-systems. Second, I will move to the evolution of the semi-peripheries in our days. Finally, I will propose a “politicization” of the concept to better understand its different roles. This politicization implies including structural geopolitical elements in the definition and analysis of the semi-periphery — particularly its intermediary nature—, which until now has been fundamentally based on the geoeconomic structure, as discussed below.

The limitations of the empirical definition of core, semi-periphery and periphery

As we have seen, the definitions of these concepts were originally made from the description of economic conditions. In fact, many of the authors who write within the world-systems analysis tradition interpret the semi-periphery primarily in economic terms. Arrighi and Drangel (1986: 15) argue that the term should only be used to “refer to a position in relation to the world division of labor and never to refer to a position in the interstate system”. Korzeniewicz (1990) basically thinks the same and makes the international division of labor the key to understanding the position of a country. Arceo (2004: 17) adopts an even more quantitative strategy, identifying the semi-periphery in 1975 with the “set of countries that had (...), at purchasing power parity, a product per capita two and a half times higher than that of the set from the periphery”.

One of the most important issues to underline then is that this division responds to a single international division of labor, which is based “on the differential appropriation of the produced surplus [so that] the positions [of the countries] are hierarchically ordered, not only differentiated” (Evans, cited in Mahutga and Smith, 2011: 257). These authors are precisely those who make an effort to quantify the degree of “centrality” of states based on the place they occupy in the international division of labor, in order to see if there is a direct relationship with economic growth (Mahutga and Smith, 2011). While this second part does not interest us now, we are going to see the differentiation they make according to the international division of labor, in which they distinguish six groups (Table 1):

- in Group 1 are the most powerful countries in the world, headed by the United States, whose production processes are marked by high technology and heavy industry;

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- Group 2 includes several European countries and some of the most dynamic countries in the developing world, including China, India, Brazil, South Korea and Singapore, whose production processes have evolved towards those of the previous group;
 - Group 3 includes most of the dynamic economies of the developing world (Indonesia, Ireland, Malaysia, Thailand or Turkey) that have evolved from a model of low wages and light manufacturing to increasingly include heavy industries;
 - Group 4 are countries with agrarian economies that have been evolving to others of low wages and light manufacturing (Peru, Honduras, Uruguay, Iran, Malta or the Ivory Coast);
 - Group 5 includes some very rich countries in terms of per capita income, which are absolutely dependent on their extractive economy, as is the case of oil producers (Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, Libya, but also Venezuela); and
 - Group 6 are the weakest (Central African Republic, Malawi or Samoa), characterized by an extractive economy that is becoming progressively more sophisticated
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Table 1. Position of countries in the world-system according to the international division of labor

<i>State and rank in 1965</i>	<i>1965</i>	<i>1980</i>	<i>2000</i>	<i>State and rank in 1965</i>	<i>1965</i>	<i>1980</i>	<i>2000</i>
1 United States (Ws)	1	1	1	48 Chili (LA)	4	3	3
2 France (Ws)	1	1	1	59 Panama (LA)	4	3	4
3 Germany (Ws)	1	1	1	49 Costa Rica (LA)	4	4	4
4 United Kingdom (Ws)	1	1	1	53 Peru (LA)	4	4	4
5 Italy (Ws)	1	1	1	55 Honduras (LA)	4	4	4
6 Japan (As)	1	1	1	58 Uruguay (LA)	4	4	4
7 Netherlands (Ws)	1	1	1	60 Iran (ME)	4	4	4
9 Canada (Ws)	1	1	1	50 Nicaragua (LA)	4	4	5
11 Belgium (Ws)	1	1	1	54 Malta (Ws)	4	4	5
8 Sweden (Ws)	1	1	2	61 Ivory Coast (Af)	4	4	5
10 Switzerland (Ws)	1	2	2	62 Iceland (Ws)	4	4	5

21 Spain (Ws)	2	2	1	51 Venezuela (LA)	4	5	4
12 Denmark (Ws)	2	2	2	63 Ecuador (LA)	4	5	4
13 Austria (Ws)	2	2	2	52 Jamaica (LA)	4	5	5
14 Czechoslovakia (EE)	2	2	2	57 Senegal (Af)	4	5	5
15 Norway (Ws)	2	2	2	64 --- (Af)	4	5	5
16 Hong Kong (As)	2	2	2	65 Ethiopia (Af)	4	5	5
17 Finland (Ws)	2	2	2	66 Paraguay (LA)	4	5	5
18 Australia (Ws)	2	2	2	56 Angola (Af)	4	6	6
19 Yugoslavia (EE)	2	2	2	70 Cyprus (Ws)	5	4	4
20 India (As)	2	2	2	73 Sri Lanka (As)	5	4	5
22 Hungary (EE)	2	2	2	78 Saudi Arabia (ME)	5	5	3
23 Portugal (Ws)	2	2	3	67 Kuwait (ME)	5	5	5
24 China (As)	3	2	2	68 Trinidad/Tobago (LA)	5	5	5
25 Argentina (LA)	3	2	2	71 Bahrein (ME)	5	5	5

26 Brazil (LA)	3	2	2	72 Libya (ME)	5	5	5
29 Ireland (Ws)	3	2	2	74 Cameroon (Af)	5	5	5
32 Singapore (As)	3	2	2	75 Jordan (ME)	5	5	5
36 South Korea (As)	3	2	2	76 Barbados (LA)	5	5	5
28 New Zealand (Ws)	3	2	3	77 Bolivia (LA)	5	5	5
30 Malaysia (As)	3	3	2	69 Ghana (Af)	5	6	5
31 Mexico (LA)	3	3	2	79 Zambia (Af)	5	6	6
37 Thailand (As)	3	3	2	91 Mauricio (Af)	6	5	5
27 Israel (ME)	3	3	3	80 Togo (Af)	6	5	6
34 Greece (Ws)	3	3	3	82 Benin (Af)	6	5	6
40 Philippines (As)	3	3	3	88 Qatar (ME)	6	6	5
41 Indonesia (As)	3	3	3	90 Brunei (As)	6	6	5
33 Morocco (ME)	3	3	4	81 Congo, Dem Rep (Af)	6	6	6
42 Turkey (ME)	3	4	3	83 Malawi (Af)	6	6	6

35 Pakistan (ME)	3	4	4	84 Gabon (Af)	6	6	6
38 Egypt (ME)	3	4	4	85 Burkina Faso (Af)	6	6	6
39 Nigeria (Af)	3	4	5	86 Niger (Af)	6	6	6
44 Colombia (LA)	4	3	4	87 Chad (Af)	6	6	6
45 Guatemala (LA)	4	4	4	89 Mali (Af)	6	6	6
46 El Salvador (LA)	4	4	4	92 Central African (Af)	6	6	6
47 Tunisia (ME)	4	4	4	93 Gambia (Af)	6	6	6
43 Algeria (ME)	4	5	5	94 Samoa (As)	6	6	6
<p>Group 1: Core; Group 2: Core-contender; Group 3: Upper-tier semiperiphery; Group 4: Strong periphery; Group 5: Weak periphery; Group 6: Weakest periphery.</p> <p>Af: Africa; As: Asia; EE: Eastern Europe; LA: Latin America; ME: Middle East; Ws: West.</p>							

Source: Mahutga y Smith (2011).

One of the advantages of this work is that, by including indices at three moments (1960, 1985 and 2000), it shows the dynamism of world production and the evolution of the international division of labor, particularly the differences between the period before and after the end of the Cold War.

The countries of Group 1 in the three moments of Table 1 (United States, France, Germany, United Kingdom, Italy, Japan, Holland, Canada and Belgium) do not offer any classificatory problem. All the authors would undoubtedly consider these as “Core”. And, evidently, the same type of core cannot be those that have been hegemonic powers in some period (Netherlands, the United Kingdom and the United States), including those that have been powers challenging that hegemony (France, Germany or Japan), that countries like Italy, Belgium or Canada, which neither were hegemonic or challenging powers. But now is not the time for that discussion.

At the other extreme, the countries in Groups 4, 5 and 6 are all classified as periphery, but the differentiation offered by Mahutga and Smith (2011) is fundamentally quantitative (strong, weak and weaker periphery). Few distinctions are made between the countries that are dedicated to light manufacturing and those that base their economy on extractivism. In a particularly interesting study, Durand, Lévy and Retailé (1992) make the world of the periphery more structurally complex, distinguishing between “integrated” peripheries, in which countries receive investment flows from the core as a result of the relocation of industries and produce for the core, “exploited” peripheries, which are incorporated into the system thanks to the exploitation of its resources, and “abandoned” peripheries, which include the poorest countries on earth, characterized rather by their disconnection from the global economic flows.

States that are in groups 2, 3 and 4 are characterized by high mobility. That is, they have characteristics of what the authors of world-systems analysis call semi-periphery. But these bands include countries as dissimilar as Sweden, Switzerland, Spain or Denmark, in the highest part of Table 1, to Ethiopia, Paraguay, Angola or Cyprus, in the lower part. This latter group, as well as the majority of those that oscillate around Group 4, are usually considered as periphery, so we are going to concentrate in the next sections on the countries of Groups 2 and 3 in the year 2000, which are the ones that Mahutga and Smith (2011) call “Core-contender” and “Upper-tier semi-periphery”. As Andersen says, the problem is “that countries as different as Norway, Iran, Nigeria, China and Italy can be conceptualized as ‘semi-peripheries’” (2016: 187). Such broad categories, covering so many different types of cases, are not very explanatory, and for this reason I think that subtypes should be established in the semi-peripheries. For this, the international division of labor is not useful; rather we must focus on the different intermediary geopolitical roles that they play.

It is true that I also believe that there are different types of core and peripheries — for example, the “integrated peripheries” of Mahutga and Smith (2011) are peripheries, but also partly encompass the “semi-periphery” of group 3— but this

discussion already exceeds the objective of this paper, and although I will make some reflections in line with the explanation, we will leave it for another time.

Mahutga and Smith (2011) point out that semi-peripheral countries contain a relatively balanced mix of core and periphery forms of production, and generally benefit from maintaining both capital-intensive and work force-intensive productions. In this way, production costs are lower than in the core, and technological capacity is greater than in the periphery, thus becoming more attractive for industrial investment. Given that the interest of these authors, as we have said, is to establish correlations between the position in the international division of labor structure and economic growth, they are especially interested in understanding the role of the semi-periphery in economic development. They conclude that “semi-peripheral countries occupy structural positions that encourage upward mobility more than peripheral countries” (Mahutga and Smith, 2011: 259). In fact, there is empirical evidence that they grow faster than the countries of the core or those of the periphery. The same authors even affirm that “the semi-periphery is converging towards the core in terms of the structure of its productive forces, but diverging from the periphery, which continues to export primary goods or light manufactures produced with low wages in the year 2000” (Mahutga and Smith, 2011: 270).

Martínez Peinado and Cairó i Cespedes (2014) abound in another type of explanation, which leads them to opposite conclusions. They also make a factorial analysis of the economies of the main core countries (those of the triad: the United States, Japan and the European Union) and some of the semi-periphery (Argentina, Brazil, China, India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Mexico, Korea South, the Russian Federation, South Africa, Thailand and Turkey, to which are added the peripheral countries of Egypt and Morocco, to see if there is a differentiated behavior of the semi-periphery with the periphery). Their aim is to understand what happens in the semi-periphery of the capitalist world-economy. To do this, they take two previous steps:

“First, we opted to move from a “commercialist” vision of the Core/Periphery conception to a “productive” vision, defined in terms of relative autonomy with respect to the Core/Periphery system, of the capital accumulation process within the framework of the “national economy”. This first step, which serves to define self-centered and extroverted economies, following Samir Amin’s terminology, has given way to a new stage in the process of capital circulation, that of global capitalism, which does not annul conceptualization, but rather redesigns the territorial spaces of application, disregarding borders, which would tend to disappear as analytically significant in the Global Capitalist System” (Martínez Peinado and Cairó i Cespedes, 2014: 256).

In the second decade of the 21st century, the extraversion of the economy in the semi-periphery —which maintains primary exporting patterns and a low manufacturing profile— continues, so that it continues to be unable to retain the surplus. The core —although with Europe lagging behind— continues to be technologically advanced. China has a unique and very contradictory role, with great weight in the world economy, but with an extroverted economy. Martínez Peinado and Cairó i Cespedes (2014: 270) conclude therefore that no “convergence” is taking

place between the semi-periphery and the core. It would be better to stop thinking of the current world system, the capitalist world-economy, as an inter-state system, and definitely assume that it is global and also consider its class structure. In this “global framework of accumulation, self-centeredness and extraversion are already defined at the supranational level.”

Summarizing, for Martínez Peinado and Cairó i Cespedes (2014):

1. The United States, the European Union and Japan (the Triad), together with China, have a great weight in the world economy.
2. The United States and Japan play a leading role in terms of technological development.
3. The economies of China and the Asian industrialized countries, a fundamental part of the semi-periphery, are strongly marked by its extraversion (mismatch between its great productive contribution *vs.* its lower participation in consumption).

How can the authors reach such different conclusions, given that both explanations are made from the analysis of production, not trade? There are two main reasons. Firstly, Martínez Peinado and Cairó i Cespedes (2014) think that we are already in another phase of the capitalist world-economy, characterized as a “global capitalist system”, while Mahutga and Smith (2011) still think in terms of an interstate system and of “national” economies. Secondly, Martínez Peinado and Cairó i Cespedes (2014) include as semi-periphery only the countries of the global South that were previously in the periphery, while in the classification of Mahutga and Smith (2011), Group 2 in the year 2000 includes Sweden, Switzerland, Denmark, Austria, Norway and Australia together with China, Brazil or India. In the same year, Group 3 includes countries such as New Zealand, Greece or Portugal along with the Philippines, Indonesia or Turkey; that is, Mahutga and Smith include in Group 3 European countries and countries of European descent that are usually classified as countries of the core.

To understand the geoeconomic role of the semi-periphery today, it is important to take into account the general value chains (GVCs) that have characterized capitalism since the 1990s. The revolution in information and communication technologies (ICT) a decade earlier allowed the displacement of the classic Fordist forms of industrial organization, which were characterized by large economic units that vertically integrated production and thus consolidated privileged positions in the market. As pointed out by Torres and Ahumada (2022: 172):

“In their place, a disintegration of these hierarchical structures and a concentration of large companies in their main areas of competence have emerged, so that the production of a merchandise has been dispersed, throughout many parts of the globe, in various productive units in charge of different inputs and parts of the product, and whose connection and governance are in charge of one or more actors.”

The central regions have concentrated on controlling “intangible” assets (technological knowledge, design, brands, computerized information) through various control procedures, including intellectual property, which allows them to

control the GVCs. In the semi-periphery, productive processes are developed that require strong capital investments and certain degrees of qualification of the labor force. In the periphery, productive processes with less technological sophistication are developed, which require a greater amount of labor that, in general, is not very qualified.

It would be worth going deeper into this economic discussion of the issue—emphasizing structural reasoning more than empirical measurements—, but I believe that a fundamental issue in the global role of the semi-periphery would be left out: its role as geopolitical intermediary. Politics is key to understanding how semi-peripheral countries are inserted into the capitalist world-economy, their evolution and even their own consideration as semi-periphery. The authors cited above agree in their explanations of the important role of the state in the growth or development of semi-peripheral countries; however, they do not deal explicitly with the issue – perhaps because both papers are fundamentally economically oriented. This is not to deny the geoeconomic nature of the semi-periphery, but to understand that it also plays a political and geopolitical role.

Politicizing and geo-politicizing the category of semi-periphery

The “objective” class structure that is defined from the international division of labor is global; in fact, most of the authors within world-systems analysis think that classes are “global strata” (Taylor and Flint, 2002: 28). However, in “subjective” terms, the social classes continue to be state, and the class struggle develops within the state.¹⁸ This is one of the reasons why the state remains important in the current world-system. The state is not an epiphenomenon that depends on the economic structure, as the most traditional orthodox Marxism claimed, but rather has its own dynamics within the world-system – yes, coupled to the international division of labor and the global class structure, which to a large extent is composed of socio-spatial classes. In other words, the “subjective” classes continue to be state—nationalists of any stripe would claim that they are also national—, and the states have a fundamental role in determining policies so that some regions are core or periphery or pass from one to the other.

As we have seen, attempts to classify states in the horizontal tripartite structure of core, semi-periphery and periphery have been fundamentally economic, since the international division of labor is the ultimate key to that division, but without considering politics it is impossible to achieve a suitable classification. And it is not just about taking into account military or other power in the abstract, as many indices of world power do (see, for example, the works of Rocha Valencia and Morales Ruvalcaba, 2010; 2018; Morales Ruvalcaba, Rocha Valencia and Vargas

¹⁸ I do not want to return here to the old Marxist discussion about class “in itself” and class “for itself”, but simply to underline what is precisely one of the great contributions of world-systems analysis to contemporary social class theory: the existence of a “division of interests” between the dominated classes of the core and the dominated classes of the periphery (Galtung, cited in Taylor and Flint, 2002: 121).

García, 2013), but to understand the internal politics and geopolitical relations in which the state finds itself.

Wallerstein was aware of the political importance of the state in the current world-system:

“From the point of view of entrepreneurs operating in a capitalist world-economy, sovereign states exercise authority over at least seven main arenas of direct interest to them: 1) States impose the rules on the exchange of goods, the capital and labor, and under what conditions they can cross its borders. 2) They create the laws concerning the property rights of states. 3) Create the rules concerning employment and compensation of employees. 4) They decide the costs that the companies must bear. 5) They decide what kind of economic processes should be monopolized, and to what extent. 6) They charge taxes. 7) Finally, when companies established within their borders may be affected, they can use their power abroad to affect the decisions of other states” (2005a: 34).

It is evident that all these elements condition production in a very important way, which obviously makes places where more benefits can be obtained more attractive for investments – for example, because low wages predominate. The industrial relocation from the core to the semi-periphery is largely explained by this procedure. But we should distinguish the (internal) political role of the state from its geopolitical role (in the interstate system).

Regarding the (internal) political role, a good part of the role of the state is that of arbitrator of the conditions of production in the territory under its jurisdiction, for which reason they continue to be decisive in the capitalist world-economy. They can, and in some cases do, become actors with their own role in the development of a country, mainly in its industrialization. This is very common in the semi-periphery, as Domingues (2012a) shows in several of the examples he studies (Korea, Taiwan, Brazil, China or India). The role is changing in each case and not all of them fit well with Evans’ (1995) developmental state model as used by Domingues. Effectively, this means that there can be development in the periphery, “dependent and associated” as Domingues emphasizes, citing Cardoso and Faletto (1972). I would add that this can also apply within the present capitalist world-economy, as shown by the transition of the People’s Republic of China from state socialism to capitalism and from the periphery to the semi-periphery —and perhaps to the core— of that world-system. In Wallerstein’s seminal article (1976: 463), it was already mentioned that both the internal politics of semi-peripheral states and their social structure are distinctive, and, in general, this question of the internal politics of states has tended to be considered.

Regarding the geopolitical role, the seventh arena to which Wallerstein (2005a) alluded, the state has a determining geopolitical role in the struggle of all states for primacy in the world-system (Agnew, 2005), since it implies an action specific foreign exchange on the part of the companies established on its borders. But this action can also be carried out by other countries or directly by transnational companies. Authors like Chase-Dunn (1990) think that political agency is a fundamental element to take into account in the semi-peripheries. Considering the cases of Mexico and Brazil, Gereffi and Evans (1981: 33) believe that “the

dependent development process is the result of the interaction of the strategies of transnational corporations with the political and economic strategies of social classes, local governments and [the policies and actions] of the states of the host countries”. Smith and Lee (1990) generally share the above arguments based on the study of the South Korean experience. Radice explains with great precision this geopolitical role of the state, which is key to the proper consideration of the semi-peripheries:

“On a global scale, there is a social division of labor between activities that generate a large part of the surplus in value chains (capital-intensive) and those that generate a smaller part (labor-intensive), which implies a self-perpetuating polarization of global resources. The existence of multiple states ensures that this polarization takes a geopolitical form, as states in which (for whatever reason) a higher proportion of core activities are located will not only have higher levels of consumption and wealth, but also more power to ensure that they will maintain or indeed increase that ratio. As companies have grown into gigantic transnational corporations, they have worked together with “their” states to set the rules of the game in trade, investment and finance that reinforce this polarization” (Radice, 2009: 12).

Originally, Wallerstein (1976) also took this question into account. In the discussion about the semi-peripheral countries of the then socialist world, he understood that many of their international relations were not dominated only by economic interest but by ideological conviction; organizing a “socialist” common market might not be the most beneficial economic option, but it would allow reaffirmation of the geopolitical opposition to the “capitalist” countries by the entire Soviet bloc.

In short, geo-politicizing the concept of semi-periphery will not only allow accurate characterization of various political strategies that could be described as “semi-peripheral” and distinguish them according to their objectives, but will also solve the problem, which we have pointed out repeatedly, of having in the same category (semi-periphery) both kind of countries: those that resemble the core countries and are closely associated with them, and those that could fit well into the periphery, with which they are closer. Let us now address this second question.

Distinguishing the semi-cores from the semi-peripheries

Few authors have tried to distinguish types of semi-periphery. Among them, Terlouw (1993) differentiated between politically strong and economically strong semi-peripheral states (Table 2), which, in very descriptive terms, allowed him to distinguish economically strong countries such as New Zealand, Ireland or Portugal, from what he determined to be politically strong countries such as Indonesia, Pakistan, Iraq, Turkey and South Korea.

Terlouw’s distinction is interesting. He understands that the great differences that exist between the countries, which are usually included in the semi-periphery, make it necessary to establish divisions in it, and he also introduces his idea that “political strength” is an important element when defining a state as semi-peripheral, at least in some cases.

Table 2. Types of semi-peripheral states (according to Terlouw, 1993)

		<i>Economic strength</i>		
		<i>Small</i>	<i>Intermediate</i>	<i>Large</i>
<i>Political strength</i>	<i>Small</i>	Periphery		Economic semi-periphery
	<i>Intermediate</i>		Ideal typical semi-periphery	
	<i>Large</i>	Political semi-periphery		Core

Source: Adapted from Terlouw (1993).

The level of political strength leads to different roles in the world-system. Already from its first formulation, Wallerstein stated that the semi-peripheral countries “partly act as a peripheral zone of the central countries and partly as a central country of some peripheral areas” (Wallerstein, 1976: 463). Later he specified: “In moments of expansion of the world-economy the (semi-peripheral) states find themselves attached as satellites to one or another central power and serve to some extent as economic transmission belts and political agents of an imperial power.” (1984: 7). In summary, it is possible to distinguish different roles and, therefore, different geopolitical positions, which could lead to different geostrategies.

Burns, Davis and Kick (1997), following the initial work of Kick (1987), also establish divisions in the semi-periphery, mainly between stronger states and weaker states, in terms of links to global networks. These are also reflected in domestic terms, such as per capita income (relatively high), urban population rate (relatively high), or occupational structure (“the population is increasingly employed in manufacturing and service occupations, which are rapidly industrializing” (Burns, Davis and Kick 1997: 440)). For the strongest states they use the name “semi-core” and for the weakest they maintain the name “semi-periphery”.¹⁹

¹⁹ Kick (1987) classifies the following countries into:

- Semi-core: Australia, Austria, Brazil, Bulgaria, China, Czechoslovakia, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Israel, New Zealand, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania and Yugoslavia.

- Semi-periphery: South Africa, Saudi Arabia, Algeria, Argentina, Bolivia, Chile, Colombia, South Korea, Costa Rica, Dominican Republic, Ecuador, Egypt, El Salvador, Philippines, Ghana, Guatemala, Guyana, Haiti, Honduras, India, Indonesia, Iran, Iraq, Jamaica, Jordan, Kenya, Kuwait, Liberia, Libya, Malaysia, Mexico, Morocco, Nicaragua, Nigeria, Pakistan, Panama, Paraguay, Peru, Singapore, Syria, Sri Lanka, Thailand, Trinidad and Tobago, Tunisia, Turkey, Uruguay, Venezuela and Zaire.

The denominations used by these authors refer more clearly to different structural positions of both countries, but the distinction is based, above all, on the intensity of certain internal socioeconomic characteristics, since it does not explain what connections to global networks consist of. This seems to me to be a fundamental key to the issue.

Chesters (2013) also distinguishes between semi-core and semi-periphery. For her, the semi-core states have political and economic systems strong enough to obtain benefits from their relations with the periphery and the semi-periphery, but “they depend on the core for capital investments, technology and military support [...] and their workers are increasingly employed in occupations in the capital-intensive manufacturing sector and in the service sector” (Chesters, 2013: 249).²⁰

The author’s objective is to examine the relationship between wealth inequality and class stratification in the capitalist economy through the analysis of the spatial distribution of the wealthiest class, the “billionaires”. Therefore, the division argument is also fundamentally economic.

In another line of reasoning, Andersen (2014; 2016) also uses the concept of “semi-core” to refer to “a specific form of historical political association in which certain imperial provinces differ from others in terms of the close relationships they maintain with the imperial metropolis” (Andersen, 2016: 178). In other words, in his case, the global geopolitical structure is fundamental in the definition. The concept is not developed within the perspective of world-systems analysis. As the author himself points out, “it is doubtful that this theory takes the specificity of empire into account analytically, since it is more concerned with the capitalist global system as a whole” (Andersen, 2016: 187). However, the same author admits that others could use the concept differently. And indeed, the examples he works on, Scotland and Norway, may be good examples of transitional spaces in the world-system, closer to the core than to the periphery, playing intermediary roles in the world-system.

In short, the semi-core are geopolitically strong states, which are particularly integrated with the central ones, so that, unlike those in the semi-periphery, they cannot be forced to “reform” their economic structures by external institutions, such as, for example, the IMF (Wallerstein, 2005b: 243). But they neither compete for hegemony in the world-system nor can be considered great powers or major powers of the system – although they can play an important regional role, even far from their location.

²⁰ Chesters’ (2013) classification is:

- Semi-core: Australia, Austria, Belgium, Canada, Denmark, Spain, Hong Kong, Ireland, Liechtenstein, Monaco, Norway, Singapore, Sweden, Switzerland and Taiwan.

- Semi-periphery: South Africa, Saudi Arabia, Argentina, Bahamas, Bahrain, Barbados, Bermuda, Brazil, Brunei, Chile, China, Cyprus, Colombia, South Korea, Costa Rica, Cuba, Dubai, Ecuador, Egypt, Emirates United Arab Emirates, Finland, Georgia, Gibraltar, Greece, Hungary, India, Indonesia, Iceland, Cayman Islands, Israel, Iraq, Kazakhstan, Kuwait, Lebanon, Macao, Malaysia, Mexico, New Zealand, Pakistan, Peru, Poland, Portugal, Qatar, Czech Republic, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Thailand, Turkey, Ukraine and Venezuela.

A good historical example is that of Portugal and its Empire during the 19th and 20th centuries, until 1974 when the April Revolution took place. Let us remember that Santos (1985) stressed that the concept of semi-periphery was associated with an intermediate situation and a certain capacity for intermediation, and mentioned the case of Portugal as an intermediary between the great powers (core) and the colonial sphere (periphery). Although Santos did not distinguish semi-cores from semi-peripheries, I think we could understand the role of Portugal as a semi-core, which is an agent of central countries in the periphery (Table 3).

Table 3. Historical intermediary relationship in Portugal until 1974 (semi-core)

	<i>Colonial relationship →</i>	
<i>Division of labor ↓</i>	England, Germany France...	
	Portugal	Angola, Cape Verde, Mozambique...

Source: Author

One of the political geostrategies of the semi-core, then, implies subordination to the core —particularly to the hegemonic power— on the one hand, and the co-optation of the periphery, through direct investments and using political alliances with semi-peripheral states on the other hand. The Portuguese-British alliance in practice meant the almost complete subordination of Portugal to the global designs of England. It implied that the relationship of this sovereign country with the hegemonic power (England) was not very different from that of Scotland, an integral part of the United Kingdom.

Semi-peripheries are also geopolitically strong states relative to the periphery: “In fact, in the south there are very large states that have real or potential geopolitical power: Russia, China, India, Brazil, Indonesia, Korea, and the list could go on” (Wallerstein, 2005b: 244). They can develop an important regional role, even global in the case of those that evolve towards the core, but in military terms they can hardly resist the attacks and challenges of the core countries, nor can they evade the political decisions of international institutions. They also play an intermediary role between the core and the periphery, but in a different structural position.

A good historical example is that of the United States with respect to the newly independent Latin American countries in the 19th century until 1861, when the Civil War broke out. When Haiti, Brazil and the territories of the Spanish Empire were gaining independence, the United States was not part of the core of the world-system. However, in both economic and geopolitical terms, it cannot be reduced to

a peripheral country. It is more appropriate to characterize it as a semi-periphery that acts with respect to the periphery included in “its” hemisphere (Table 4). Economically, it slowly began to invest in the region, especially in the closest part—the Caribbean—and geopolitically it was opposed to European countries. This is shown in the statement of President James Monroe during his Sixth Address to Congress on the State of the Union in 1823, which gave rise to the so-called Monroe Doctrine. On that occasion, the US president issued a serious warning to the European countries regarding their possible intervention in the affairs of the Western hemisphere – “his hemisphere”. Although its immediate effect, in terms of the defence of the new American states, was purely moral—since his economic interests and his political and military capacity were quite limited—the Latin American leaders of the time appreciated it.

Table 4. Historical intermediary relationship of the United States until 1861 (semi-periphery)

	<i>Geopolitical opposition →</i>	
<i>Economic investment ↑</i>	Mexico, Argentina, Colombia...	
	United States	England, Spain, France...

Source: Author

In 1875, at the end of the British geopolitical order, the United States had ceased to be an autonomous semi-periphery and was a core power. Its economy was thriving and highly productive, and it was engaged in an imperial expansion that implied formally and, above all, informally to Latin America. The relationship with this region and with the rest of the world changed radically.

In the next two sections, I will illustrate the hypothesis on the differentiation between semi-core and semi-peripheries with a brief study of several cases.

Semi-core in Southern Europe after the Cold War

The Southern European region is perfectly suited to show the characteristics of semi-core, in both geoeconomic and geopolitical terms. According to the classification by Mahutga and Smith (2011) above, Spain, Portugal and Greece would be in groups 2 and 3 during the period analyzed, which we have considered to be the semi-peripheries. However, due to their geopolitical role, we will try to show that we should consider them as semi-core. Italy must also be included, which in geoeconomic terms is comparable to others only in relation to its southern half, but in geopolitical terms its role is more similar to that of Spain.

Hadjimichalis (1987) convincingly describes the semi-peripheralization of the region in three phases:

1. The transition of Western Southern Europe from the core to the semi-periphery (and even the periphery) between the late 16th and 18th centuries due to the drive of capitalism in Northwestern Europe and the emergence of a relatively coherent world market. The Greek territories of the Ottoman Empire, from their peripheral situation, also suffered from this process.
2. The industrialization of England from the middle of the 18th century, the independence of the American colonies in the first third of the 19th century and the war in Africa were going to destroy the markets of Spain, Portugal and the industries of the Piedmont valley. In Greece, the artisan manufacturing cores were destroyed, preventing any industrial take-off. From this time comes the double North-South divide in Europe: not only between Northern Europe (especially North-western) and Southern Europe, but also within Southern Europe itself.
3. Since the last third of the 19th century, North-western European imperialism played a more active role in the southern part of the continent, making investments (especially in the railways) and granting loans to governments, which socially and spatially transformed the region. While Spain and Italy struggled to establish the unity of their states and Greece struggled to liberate all the Greek territories from Ottoman rule, the stabilization of the conditions of capitalist accumulation in the north of the continent allowed it to dominate the south.

And to these phases I would add two more:

4. The situation will change in the second half of the 20th century: the rapid industrialization process, the construction of large infrastructures and the intensification of state intervention build certain integrated national economic spaces. The conservative and/or authoritarian governments of Portugal (1933-1974) and Spain (1939-1975), the anti-communist one in Greece after the civil war, which ended in a military dictatorship (1967-1974), and the right-wing Christian Democrats in Italy (1946-1994), all oriented themselves towards “developmentalism”. This ended the dominant role of the landed bourgeoisie, partly also because industrialization did not take place in traditional places, breaking to some extent the logic of industrial norths and agricultural souths.
5. Although Italy was one of the founding states of the European Economic Community in 1958, the other countries of southern Europe joined the EEC in 1981 (Greece) and 1986 (Spain and Portugal). Their entry into what is now the European Union led most scholars, in a short time, to stop considering them as semi-periphery and to consider them as part of the core, although in the case of Greece often with reluctance. But none of them played a role in the EU or in the world similar to that of Germany or even the Netherlands, as was seen quite clearly, especially from the Great

Recession that began in 2008 and the deficit and balance of payments problems that emerged clearly in all of them. The acronym PIGS (Portugal-Italy-Greece-Spain), with a clearly pejorative meaning, was used to designate the southern EU countries in Anglo-Saxon and northern European political, financial and journalistic circles. Even Ireland, which had similar problems forming the PIIGS acronym, was included.

A) Semi-core articulating the relationship between core and peripheries: Contemporary Spain and Portugal

In the opinion of Santos (1985), the historical condition of Portugal as a semi-peripheral country was maintained even after the end of Portugal’s formal sovereignty over the colonial territories. Portugal’s incorporation into the European Union in 1986 would only have reinforced this semi-core role. To some extent, this would now be more reminiscent of Andersen’s Scotland and Norway, since Portugal would be integrated into that supranational political unit. And the creation in 1996 of an organization in the style of the British Commonwealth with its colonies, the Community of Portuguese Language Countries (*Comunidade dos Países de Língua Portuguesa*, CPLP), made it possible to better articulate this intermediary relationship between Portugal, already a member of the EU, with the countries of America, Africa, Asia, and Oceania whose language is Portuguese.

Table 5. Intermediary relationship between Spain and Portugal, 1986-2020 (core □ semi-core □ far away peripheries)

	<i>Relationship of geoeconomic and geocultural domination</i>	
<i>Division of labor</i>	Germany, Netherlands, France...	
	Spain / Portugal	Argentina, Costa Rica, Peru... / Angola, Mozambique, Cape Verde...

Source: Author

The Spanish case is similar. The incorporation in the EU in the same year also allows their access to the core. In Table 2 we saw that Spain was in Group 2 in 1960 and in 1985, but in the year 2000 it was already in Group 1 (Mahutma and Smith, 2011). I think this is consistent with its new geopolitical role since the 1980s, which implies not only belonging to the EU but also intermediation (Table 5) with the main Latin American countries. This is thanks to the strong investments of “Spanish” transnationals in the region (Arahuetes, 2011), which between 1990 and 2000 were second only to those of the United States. The construction of the structures of the

Ibero-American Community of Nations (CIN) (Cairo and Ríos, 2018), similar to those of the CPLP, have given rise to a relatively consolidated interregionalism (Cairo, 2019) – which, by the way, despite the subordination to the political geostrategies of the core countries, does not exclude the emergence of an interregionalism of resistance (Bringel and Cairo, 2019).

B) Semi-core separating the core and nearby peripheries: Italy and Greece

Although their trajectories in the modern world-system and their situations in the international division of labor are different, Italy and Greece play similar geopolitical roles to other southern European countries today. Since the creation of the Schengen area in 1985, both countries together with Spain have formed the southern border of Europe. Migratory pressure on Italy comes especially from Libya in North Africa, and on Greece from Turkey in East Asia (Table 6).

These are two examples of a semi-periphery that is spatially located between the central and peripheral regions, one of the roles identified by Chase-Dunn and Hall (2018) for this type of area. In the case of Italy, this is especially true of the southern regions. It is a geopolitical task imposed by the core countries, in this case from the EU.

Table 6. Intermediary relationship between Italy and Greece, 1981-2020 (core □ semi-core □ near peripheries)

	<i>Relation of exclusion</i>	
<i>Division of labor</i>	Germany, Netherlands, France...	
	Southern Italy / Greece	Libya, Tunisia... / Turkey, Egypt.....

Source: Author

C) Semi-core intermediating core-core: Ireland

Another type of semi-core has a role in mediating the interests of a core country in other core countries. An example is the case of Ireland after its entry into the then European Economic Community in 1973 (Table 7). It is true that Ireland is not located in Southern Europe, but it is perfectly assimilable, as the acronym PIGS shows. Coakley rightly notes that “in the ‘Celtic Tiger’ years Ireland experienced a growth rate of 6% [...] Ireland became a conduit through which American companies entered the European market. A significant pull factor [...] was the low

tax rate and the numerous tax exemption formulas” (2016: 184). The policies of the Irish state made foreign investment in this country attractive.

In geopolitical terms, Ireland’s relationship with the United States is somewhat similar to Spain’s relationship with Latin America, obviously changing the direction of the flows and their intensity; its role as a “bridge” is based on cultural and/or political elements common to two intervening spatial ensembles.

Table 7. *Intermediary relationship of Ireland, 1970-2020 (core □ semicore □ core)*

	<i>Integration relationship</i>	
<i>Division of labor</i>	United States...	
	Ireland	Germany, France Netherlands...

Source: Author

Now, once the semi-core has been defined based on certain elements of the semi-periphery, we have to return to this category to see if it is convenient to make more identification details, when taking into account the geopolitical role of states.

Distinguishing subordinate and autonomous semi-peripheries in Latin America after the Cold War

The structural location of the semi-periphery allows greater freedom of action and mobility for social movements and their political representatives, while in the core or the periphery, class relations are more established. In addition, the interests of the ruling classes in the semi-periphery are usually divided between those who seek alliances with the core countries to maintain their peripheral-type productions and those who want to promote and expand their core-type activities. As discussed, the classic example is the United States: the confrontation between the industrialized North and the slave-owning and agrarian South ended in the Civil War, the outcome of which placed the United States at the core of the world system. Katz (2011) makes a very good argument for China today about the alternatives offered to the ruling classes: extraverted growth, at the cost of greater exploitation of the Chinese proletariat, or endogenous growth, which would imply improving the living conditions of the population in general.

In Latin America we can see quite clearly the two examples of geostrategy after the end of the Cold War: one of “subordination” and the other of “autonomy”. In geoeconomic terms, they coincide with two of the types of Latin American

capitalisms that Bizberg (2019) talks about: subordination with “international outsourcing capitalism” and autonomy with “neo- or socio-developmental”.

Wallerstein’s (1976) original definition of semi-periphery included six Latin American countries (Argentina, Chile, Brazil, Venezuela, Cuba, and Mexico). During the Cold War, and after the Castro revolution, Cuba played an intermediary geopolitical role between the USSR and peripheral countries of both Latin America (Colombia, El Salvador, Guatemala and Peru, among others) and Africa (Angola and Ethiopia, in particular). Cuba supported the insurgencies that the USSR supported in these countries or supported pro-Soviet post-colonial states against pro-Western insurgencies. Venezuela and Chile could have had thriving economies and intermediate roles in the international division of labor, but to a large extent both lost those characteristics in the post-Cold War period. The fact is that there are currently three Latin American countries that are usually identified by most authors as semi-peripheral: Argentina, Brazil and Mexico. The place they occupy in the international division of labor indicates this, and, as we will see, their geopolitical role confirms it.

A) The geostrategy of subordination in the semi-periphery: The case of Mexico

The geostrategy of subordination implies a relationship with the core, similar to that of the semi-core – although from another structural position. This could be perfectly exemplified by the doctrine of “peripheral realism” (Escudé, 1992), which

“is based on the implicit assumption that in the interstate order there are written and unwritten rules, and that, despite our regrets, the most powerful states have a preponderant role in establishing those rules [...] A few have the power that it allows them to contribute to forging the rules of the game, while the vast majority is forced to behave according to the rules established by this oligopoly. And there is also a third category of states that, without having the power to contribute to establishing these rules, rebel against them, paying very high costs that revert to their inhabitants” (Escudé, 2012: 532-4).

Table 8. Intermediary relationship in Mexico, 1989-2020 (subordinate semi-periphery)

	<i>Dominance relationship</i>	
<i>División of labor</i>	United States...	
	Mexico	Guatemala, Honduras, El Salvador...

Source: Author

From this analysis, it can be deduced that the only “logical” policy for a semi-periphery is to yield to the designs of the countries of the core. Escudé theorized peripheral realism based on Argentine foreign policy, a semi-peripheral country, but

with geostrategies that have oscillated between subordination and autonomy. That is why I think that Mexico is a clearer case of Bizberg's first type (Table 8).

The intermediary mechanisms of Mexico in relation to the core, particularly the United States, are articulated through numerous US economic investments in Mexico, which have especially developed maquila-type production in this country. Formally, the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) is the main link, but this division of labor is also supported by mechanisms of political subjection. All the governments of Mexico of the period, even that of Andrés Manuel López Obrador, have accommodated themselves to this situation.

In turn, Mexico's domination of the Central American space is articulated through various geopolitical projects that have legal instruments, such as the Puebla Panama Plan (PPP) or the Tuxtla Gutiérrez Treaty, which sought to create a free trade area in Mexico and Central America.

The iron control of the southern border of Mexico—to which the government of López Obrador committed to the US' Trump administration in exchange for stopping the construction of the wall on its northern border—is another good example of the subordinate geostrategy by which Mexico's role is determined, which goes beyond even the alternation of governments of opposing political signs.

B) The geostrategy of autonomy in the semi-periphery: the case of Brazil

But the geostrategy of subordination is not the only possible type. Geostrategies of autonomy are also developed (the rebellions to which Escudé referred) and this is possible because, as Chase-Dunn points out, the semi-periphery is a space of opportunity for social movements and progressive governments:

The idea that the core/periphery hierarchy cuts across and harmonizes class relations in the core, and sometimes in the periphery, but that class struggles in the semi-periphery are not so mute, and thus transformative social movements, the ones that really challenge the logic of capitalism, tend to form and be more successful in the semi-periphery (1990: 2).

The resistance of semi-peripheral peoples to domination and exploitation from the core also provides a sample of the class struggle at a global level (Anderson and Chase-Dunn, 2005).

There is not a single autonomy geostrategy. They can be diverse, since there are different mechanisms to form it, and there can be multiple combinations. However, in general, all of them will use:

- Economic protection against international competition, particularly with respect to the productive sectors of the core.
- Strengthening of autonomous integration processes, such as CELAC, vis-à-vis the OAS and other supra-Latin American integration spaces.
- Coordination of policies with other semi-peripheral countries of the global South, such as India, China or Brazil.

In general, they can be summarized in the practice of affirming one's own voice in regional affairs; trying to weave autonomous alliances, and avoiding the follow-on of the hegemonic power in international affairs; and trying to agree with other powers that also develop autonomous geostrategies. Here we consider the case of Brazil, during the presidencies of Lula da Silva and Dilma Rouseff (Table 9).

Table 9. Intermediary relationship in Brazil, 2003-2015 (autonomous semi-periphery)

		<i>Relationship of internal alliance</i>	<i>Relationship of extra-regional agreement</i>
<i>Division of labor</i>	United States, European Union, Japan...		
	Brazil	MERCOSUR, CELAC...	China India African Atlantic countries...

Source: Author

During this period, Brazil was one of the main promoters of the autonomous integration processes in Latin America, such as UNASUR or CELAC. At the same time, Brazil agreed with other peripheries of the global South in various fora, such as the World Trade Organization, and in particular, promoted South-South cooperation within the BRICS.

The impulse of UNASUR and, within it, the creation of the South American Defense Council (CDS) in 2008 (Sanahuja and Verdes-Montenegro, 2014), had the aim of consolidating the region as a zone of peace, building an identity in defence and strengthening cooperation in the military field. Despite the fact that the UNASUR crisis is very deep (Bragatti, 2019), the creation of the CDS has favored the increase in trust between the states of the region. This is essential for the maintenance of regional peace and that favors its autonomous political integration.

In earlier times (for example, during the period of the military dictatorship) Brazil developed semi-peripheral geostrategies of subordination. The concept of “sub-imperialism” by Ruy Mauro Marini (1974; 1977) alludes to this period, and while it is certainly similar to that developed here, once again we find ourselves with a concept defined fundamentally from an economic basis:

“Sub-imperialism corresponds to the emergence of intermediate points in the organic composition of capital worldwide, as it progresses in the integration of production systems, as well as the arrival of a dependent economy at the stage of monopoly and financial capital. Likewise, Brazil can be identified as the purest expression of sub-imperialism, in our days” (Marini, 1974: 7).

It takes into account that it favors the “greater integration of the capitalist productive system and at the same time maintains the hegemony exercised by imperialism on the international scale” (Marini, 1977: 17). Marini identifies Brazil as the best example of sub-imperialism of the time, along with Mexico and Argentina in Latin America.

Conclusion

The introduction of political elements in the definition of the intermediate categories of the tripartite horizontal structure of the modern world-system allows us to successfully differentiate the states that we have called “semi-core” from those that we continue to consider “semi-periphery”. Both categories have an intermediary role, but the structural position they occupy in the world-system is different: the former are more articulated with the core, while the latter are more with the periphery.

Most of the authors define countries that make up the semi-periphery based on their role in the international division of labor and use economic data to differentiate them empirically. Geo-politicizing them has allowed us to better differentiate the semi-periphery from the semi-core, but it is important to understand that the need to geo-politicize the concepts of semi-core and semi-periphery does not mean that they do not have to be defined in geoeconomic terms as well. It must be remembered that the objective of this article was to complement the geoeconomic definition of semi-periphery, not to replace it.

The southern European semi-core have demonstrated their close geopolitical relationship with the core countries, to which they actually belong, and that precisely allows them to develop their intermediary relationship of domination with respect to not only distant or near peripheries, but also between different parts of the core area of the world-system.

The semi-periphery, unlike the semi-core, is framed in the periphery of the world-system, occupying its most dynamic segment which is in transition. It occupies an intermediary role in the general chain of production values. The semi-periphery are powerful geopolitically countries, and on many occasions, moreover, are large.

By politicizing the category of semi-periphery, we have also been able to differentiate two groups of geostrategies of these states: one that includes those more oriented to serve as a transmission belt for the core, and another that includes those that seek the autonomous development of the peoples of the South.

We were able to identify in geoeconomic terms the Latin American semi-peripheries after the geopolitical order of the Cold War, and we saw the contrasts in the characteristics of their economies, in particular their more extroverted or more self-centred character. In geopolitical terms, we find that they develop different geostrategies in the world-system, one more of subordination and another one of autonomy. In the Post-Cold War, Mexico is a good example of the first and Brazil

of the second (at least during the governments of Lula da Silva and Dilma Rouseff). The case of Argentina, which we have not dealt with, is in principle more ambiguous. Hypothetically, during the Kirchner governments, geostrategies of autonomy were adopted, while in the Macri government, geostrategies of subordination were developed, but the distinction does not seem to be so clear.

In short, the cases studied allow us to better support the hypothesis that (geo)politicizing the analysis of the semi-peripheries—that is, also reasoning about them in both geopolitical and geoeconomic terms—allows us to better explain the intermediary roles of these intermediate spaces in the modern world-system.

Scientific classifications cannot have a mere taxonomic purpose, which risk falling into a fatuous rhetorical exercise. I hope that the clarifications made in this article contribute to clarifying the concept of semi-periphery, that most authors consider to be obscure.

References

- AGNEW, John. (2005), *Geopolítica: una (re)visión de la política mundial*. Madrid: Trama Editorial (ed. original en inglés 2003).
- ANDERSEN, Morten Skumsrud. (2014), What was Norway's Role in the Danish Empire? Scotland and Norway as Semi-Cores. *Internasjonal Politikk*, 72(3), 366-387.
- ANDERSEN, Morten Skumsrud. (2016), Semi-cores in imperial relations: The cases of Scotland and Norway. *Review of International Studies*, 42(1), 178-203.
- ANDERSON, Eugene N., y CHASE-DUNN, Christopher. (2005), The rise and fall of great powers. En E. N. Anderson y C. Chase-Dunn (eds). *The Historical Evolution of World-Systems*, pp. 1-19. Nueva York: Palgrave.
- ARAHUETES, Alfredo. (2011), Las inversiones directas españolas en América Latina en el período 2001-2010. En C. Malamud Rikles, F. Steinberg y C. Tejedor (eds.). *Anuario Iberoamericano 2011*, pp. 67-85. Madrid: Agencia EFE / Real Instituto Elcano.
- ARCEO, Enrique (2004). La crisis del modelo neoliberal en la Argentina I (y los efectos de la internacionalización de los procesos productivos en la semiperiferia y la periferia). *Realidad Económica*, (206), 10-28.
- ARRIGHI, Giovanni, y DRANGEL, Jessica. (1986), The stratification of the world-economy: an exploration of the semiperipheral zone. *Review*, X(1), 9-74.
- BIZBERG, Ilán. (2019), *Diversity of Capitalisms in Latin America*. Cham (Suiza): Springer International Publishing (edición de Kindle).
- BRAGATTI, Milton Carlos. (2019), Ten Years of the South American Defense Council: Regional International Security Architecture. *Geopolítica(s). Revista de estudios sobre espacio y poder*, 10(1), 69-86.
- BRINGEL, Breno, y CAIRO, Heriberto. (2019), Interregionalism from below: cultural affinity, translation and solidarities in the Ibero-American space. En H. Cairo y B. Bringel (eds). *Critical Geopolitics and Regional (Re)Configurations: Interregionalism and Transnationalism between Latin America and Europe*, pp. 161-176. Londres y Nueva York: Routledge.
- BURNS, Thomas J.; DAVIS, Byron L., y KICK, Edward L. (1997), Positions in the world-system and national emissions of greenhouse gases. *Journal of World-Systems Research*, 3(3), 432-466.
- CAIRO, Heriberto. (2019), Euro-Latin American interregionalism in the new post-Cold War geopolitical order. En H. Cairo y B. Bringel (eds). *Critical Geopolitics and Regional (Re)Configurations: Interregionalism and Transnationalism between Latin America and Europe*, pp. 63-76. Londres y Nueva York: Routledge.

-
- CAIRO, Heriberto, y RÍOS, Jerónimo. (2019), América Latina: Las incertidumbres de las nuevas integraciones latinoamericanas más abiertas al mundo. En J. A. Preciado Coronado (coord. gen.): *Dimensiones, estrategias y alternativas de la integración autónoma para América Latina y el Caribe. Desafíos para el caso mexicano (2010-2015)* (Tomo II: “Política, Geopolítica y Ecología Política”), pp. 223-253. Guadalajara: Universidad de Guadalajara.
- CARDOSO, Fernando Henrique, y FALETTTO, Enzo. (1972), *Dependencia y desarrollo en América Latina: ensayo de interpretación sociológica*. México: Siglo XXI (ed. original 1969).
- CHASE-DUNN, Christopher. (1990), Resistance to imperialism: semiperipheral actors. *Review*, XIII(1), 1-32.
- CHASE-DUNN, Christopher, y HALL, Thomas D. (2018), *Rise and demise: comparing world-systems*. Nueva York y Abingdon: Routledge (edición de Kindle) (1ª ed 1997).
- CHESTERS, Jenny. (2013), Wealth Inequality and Stratification in the World Capitalist Economy. *Perspectives on Global Development and Technology*, 12, 246-265.
- COAKLEY, Maurice. (2016), Ireland, Europe and the Global Crisis. *Journal of World-Systems Research*, 22(1), 177-201.
- DOMINGUES, José Mauricio. (2012a), *Desarrollo, periferia y semiperiferia en la tercera fase de la modernidad global*. Ciudad Autónoma de Buenos Aires: CLACSO.
- DOMINGUES, José Mauricio. (2012b), *Global Modernity, Development, and Contemporary Civilization: Towards a Renewal of Critical Theory*. Nueva York y Abingdon: Routledge.
- DURAND, Marie-Françoise; LÉVY, Jacques, y RETAILLÉ, Denis. (1992), *Le monde: espaces et systèmes*. Paris: Presses de la Fondation nationale des sciences politiques & Dalloz.
- ESCODÉ, Carlos. (1992), *Realismo Periférico*. Buenos Aires: Planeta.
- ESCODÉ, Carlos. (2012), El realismo periférico (RP) y su relevancia teórica ante el ascenso de China. *Desarrollo Económico*, 51(204), 529-542.
- EVANS, Peter. (1995), *Embedded Autonomy: States and Industrial Transformation*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- FRANK, Andre Gunder. (1967), El desarrollo del subdesarrollo. *Pensamiento Crítico*, 7, 159-172.
- GEREFFI, Gary, y EVANS, Peter B. (1981), Transnational corporations, dependent development and state policy in the semiperiphery: a comparison of Brazil and Mexico. *Latin American Research Review*, 16(3), 31-64.

-
- KATZ, Claudio. (2011), *Bajo el imperio del capital*. Buenos Aires: Luxemburg.
- KICK, Edward L. (1987), World-System Structure, National Development, and the Prospects for a Socialist World Order. En T. Boswell y A. Berges (eds.). *America's Changing Role in the World-System*, pp. 127-155. Nueva York: Praeger.
- KORZENIEWICZ, Roberto Patricio. (1990), The limits to semiperipheral development: Argentina in the twentieth century. En W. G. Martin (ed.). *Semiperipheral States in the World-Economy*, pp. 97-122. Nueva York: Greenwood Press.
- LEFEBVRE, Henri. (1974), *La production de l'espace*. París: Éditions Anthropos.
- LIJPHART, Arend. (1971). Comparative Politics and Comparative Method. *American Political Science Review*, 65(3), 682-693.
- MAHUTGA, Matthew C., y SMITH, David A. (2011), Globalization, the structure of the world economy and economic development. *Social Science Research*, 40(1), 257-272.
- MARINI, Ruy Mauro. (1974), *Subdesarrollo y revolución*. Buenos Aires: Siglo XXI.
- MARINI, Ruy Mauro. (1977), La acumulación capitalista mundial y el subimperialismo. *Cuadernos Políticos*, 12. México: Ediciones Era [En línea. Disponible en URL: <http://www.marinescritos.unam.mx/006_acumulacion_es.htm>. Revisado el 12/12/2015].
- MARTÍNEZ PEINADO, Javier, y CAIRÓ I CESPEDES, Gemma. (2014), La Semiperiferia Como Necesidad del Capitalismo Global: Una Aproximación a Través del Análisis Factorial. *Revista de Economía Mundial*, 38, 253-272.
- MORALES RUVALCABA, Daniel Efrén; ROCHA VALENCIA, Alberto, y VARGAS GARCÍA, Elizabeth. (2013), Las potencias regionales como protagonistas del sistema político internacional: cooperación y diálogo en el Foro BRICS. *Geopolítica(s). Revista de estudios sobre espacio y poder*, 4(2), 237-261.
- RADICE, Hugo. (2009), Halfway to Paradise? Making Sense of the Semiperiphery. *Working Paper CSGP 09/3*, Trent University, Peterborough, Ontario, Canada [En línea. Disponible en URL: <www.trentu.ca/globalpolitics>. Revisado el 10/03/2018].
- ROCHA VALENCIA, Alberto, y MORALES RUVALCABA, Daniel Efrén. (2010), Potencias medias y potencias regionales en el sistema político internacional: dos modelos teóricos. *Geopolítica(s). Revista de estudios sobre espacio y poder*, 1(2), 251-279.
- ROCHA VALENCIA, Alberto, y MORALES RUVALCABA, Daniel. (2018), El poder nacional-internacional de los Estados. Una propuesta

transestructural". *Geopolítica(s). Revista de estudios sobre espacio y poder*, 9(1), 137-169.

- SANAHUJA, José Antonio, y Verdes-Montenegro, Francisco. (2014). Seguridad y defensa en Suramérica: regionalismo, cooperación y autonomía en el marco de UNASUR. En A. Serbin, L. Martínez y H. Ramanzini Jr. (coords.). *Anuario de la integración en América Latina y el Caribe 2014*. Buenos Aires: CRIES, Recuperado de https://www.academia.edu/9270335/Seguridad_y_defensa_en_Suramérica_a_regionalismo_cooperación_y_autonom%C3%ADa_en_el_marco_de_UNASUR.
- SANTOS, Boaventura de Sousa. (1985), Estado e sociedade na semiperiferia do sistema mundial: o caso português. *Análise Social*, XXI(87-88-89), 869-901.
- SARTORI, Giovanni. (1991), Comparing and Miscomparing. *Journal of Theoretical Politics*, 3(3), 243-257.
- SARTORI, Giovanni, y MORLINO, Leonardo (comp.). (1999), *La comparación en las ciencias sociales*. Madrid: Alianza Editorial (ed. original en italiano 1991).
- SMITH, David A., y LEE, Soo H. (1990), Limits on a semiperipheral success story? State dependent development and the prospects for South Korean democratization. En W. G. Martin (ed.). *Semiperipheral States in the World-Economy*, pp. 79-95. Nueva York: Greenwood Press.
- TAYLOR, Peter J., y FLINT, Colin. (2002), *Geografía Política: Economía Mundo, Estado-Nación y Localidad*. (2ª ed). Madrid: Trama Editorial (ed. original en inglés 2000).
- TERLOUW, C. P. (1993), The Elusive Semiperiphery: A Critical Examination of the Concept of Semiperiphery. *International Journal of Comparative Sociology*, 34(1-2), 87-102.
- TORRES, Miguel, y AHUMADA, José Miguel. (2022), Las relaciones centro-periferia en el siglo XXI. *El Trimestre Económico*, LXXXIX(1), 151-195.
- WALLERSTEIN, Immanuel. (1976), Semi-Peripheral Countries and the Contemporary World Crisis. *Theory and Society*, 3(4), 461-483.
- WALLERSTEIN, Immanuel. (1984), *The Politics of the World-Economy*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- WALLERSTEIN, Immanuel. (2005a), *Análisis de sistemas-mundo. Una introducción*. México D.F.: Siglo XXI Editores (ed. original en inglés 2004).
- WALLERSTEIN, Immanuel. (2005b), *La decadencia del poder estadounidense: Estados Unidos en un mundo caótico*. Montevideo y Santiago de Chile: Trilce & Lom (ed. original en inglés 2003).